

Evaluation of Industrial and Municipal Wastewaters as Bio-Stimulants for the Treatment of Crude oil Contaminated Soils

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Abstract

The prevalence and high rate of soil contamination have contributed immensely to the reduction of arable lands which might lead to the total annihilation of the ecosystem if not mitigated. Bioremediation employs microorganisms that offer a sustainable approach for the remediation of contaminated soils. This study focus on the evaluation of industrial (brewery) and municipal effluents for the treatment of crude oil-contaminated soil. A microcosm containing 1kg of crude oil contaminated soil was amended with the brewery and municipal wastewater at different ratios to investigate the possible synergy. The result of the 28 days study conducted at mesophilic condition recorded 58.39% and 56.62% TPH removal efficiencies for the brewery and municipal wastewater which represents 29195 and 28310mg/kg respectively average TPH removal from 50,000mg/kg initial concentration. The study showed that wastewater could serve as a potentially cost-effective and eco-friendly alternative for the remediation of crude oil contaminated soils.

Keywords: Brewery and Municipal Wastewater, Crude oil, contaminated soil, Biostimulation, Biodegradation,

1 Introduction

The accumulation of high concentrations of harmful (toxic) substances in the ecosystem is subject to environmental contamination and ecological imbalances, which have led to the gradual deterioration of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. This release of these toxic substances can be linked to anthropogenic, human, and industrial activities such as mineral mining and crude oil production and processing. Crude oil is an important raw material needed for the manufacture of petroleum-based products such as premium motor spirit, dual-purpose kerosene, and automated gas oil, which serve as an energy source for industry and everyday life. Crude oil pollution of soil or water can be due to spillage attributed to oil rig blow-out during drilling operations and from tankers, pipelines, or refineries during the transportation, pipeline breakage, or refining of crude oil respectively (Fig. 1). Due to its prevalence and the prolific threat posed to the ecosystem's survival, this form of pollution has become a serious issue of global concern as the constant use of crude oil as an energy source increases the risk of soil pollution, which necessitate the development of a sustainable approach for the reclamation of contaminated soils.

Previous methods (Physical, Chemical, Thermal, Encapsulation, and Electrochemical methods) of remediation of crude oil contaminated soils have some room

for improvement to render effective treatment. However, these approaches have been criticized due to its expensive and non-eco-friendly nature which made site reclamation a difficult task [1], [2]. Bioremediation provides the application of organic or inorganic nutrients (biostimulation), or injection of air or oxygen (bioventing), the introduction of genetically modified strain/consortium (bioaugmentation) or the use of plants (phytoremediation) and/or associated microbes for the reduction of contaminant concentration in the environment to facilitate remediation [3-6] and these methods have been validated by different studies [7-12].

This study aims to evaluate the application of industrial and municipal wastewaters as biostimulants for the treatment of crude oil-contaminated soil.

Figure. 1a and b: Crude oil spillage in Durban, South Africa - Polluted the soil and emptied into the Umbilo River (Source; South Durban Community Environmental Alliance, SDCEA – 19th Oct. 2020)

1.1 The motivation for the selection of wastewater effluents for this study

- Readily available for utilization
- Ease of application
- Contains appreciable organic components
- Pose no risk to soil organic matter component
- Cost-effective (Requires no pre-treatment)
- Sustainability (eco-friendly)
- Improves waste management

2 Materials and Method

2.1 Materials

- Soil samples were collected from Durban, South Africa (pH – 7.3)
- Industrial (Brewery wastewater, BWW) and Municipal wastewaters were collected from South Africa Brewery (SAB) and South African local wastewater treatment facility respectively and characterized as shown in Table 1.
- Crude oil was collected from Local Oil Refinery Company, South Africa

2.2 Methodology

- Preparation of crude oil contaminated soil: 50g of crude oil was mixed with 1kg of soil and agitated to achieve a homogenous mixture.
- Experimental set-up: Biostimulation (BSTc) study consists of 5 bioreactors with varying loadings of BWW and MWW (Table 2) for 28 days study period. One bioreactor for Bioattenuation (BATc) was used as the control treatment.

Table 1. Wastewater Properties

Wastewater/ Composition	BWW	MWW
COD (mg/l)	750	704
pH	8.5	8

Table 2. Biostimulation (BSTc) treatment composition

Bioreactors	BWW (mg/kg ⁻¹) Soil	MWW (mg/kg ⁻¹) Soil
BSTc-1	100	0
BSTc-2	75	25
BSTc-3	50	50
BSTc-4	25	75
BSTc-5	0	100
BATc (Control)	0	0

2.3 Analytical Procedure

- COD was determined according to method 5220D, *Standard Methods* (APHA 1995) using COD reactor (Hach, USA) and Spectrophotometry (DR 3900).
- Soil pH was determined (according to Peech *et al.* 1945) using an electronic pH meter

2.4 Sample Preparation

- Sample drying – In the oven at 35°C
- Sample pulverization – using mortar and pestle to ensure homogeneity
- Mechanical extraction was used to extract residue crude oil from soil samples by dissolving the sample in dichloromethane and acetone (2:1) and agitated rigorously in a mechanical shaker

2.5 Sample Analysis

GCMS analysis was carried out on samples to determine Total Petroleum Hydrocarbon (TPH) residue after the treatment using Shimadzu GCMS-QP2010 SE.

3 Results and Discussion

Figure 1 showed a gradual reduction in TPH concentration with an increase in treatment time. The modification of contaminated soil with wastewater improves microbial activities, as evident in the weekly increase in TPH removal efficiency from the first week of treatment to the fourth week (Fig. 2). This can be attributed to the ability of wastewater to stimulate the contaminated environment and provides appreciable organic nutrients to the indigenous soil bacteria for effective biodegradation. The relationship between microbial growth and biodegradation rate is proportional to increased TPH removal as confirmed in several studies [7-11]. Also, organic substrates such as municipal and brewery wastewaters can be used as pH regulators, organic substitutes, soil conditioners, and natural surfactants to enhance oil solubility for improved bioavailability of hydrocarbons to degrading bacteria [13]. [14] reported that the use of organic nutrients facilitates mobilization of degrading strains which break down and consumed these hydrocarbons and convert them into usable biomass for metabolic activities [14-18]. However, brewery wastewater (BSTc-1) showed slightly appreciable removal efficiency with 59% which represents 29195mg/kg TPH removed from 50,000mg/kg initial TPH concentration when compared with municipal wastewater, BSTc-5 with 57% (28310mg/kg TPH removed) which (BWW appreciable removal) is due to the high organic nutrients that accounts for the high microbial load for effective biodegradation. This also explains the reason behind the result recorded by the mixed substrate (BST-2, 3, and 4) with an average removal efficiency of 50% (24525mg/kg TPH removed) which is slightly below single substrate treatments. The control treatment (BAT) recorded the least TPH removal efficiency (35%) due to lack of organic amendment.

Figure 1. TPH removal (mg/kg) from the treatment

Figure 2. Evaluation of removal efficiencies of different treatments

The result of this investigation which recorded 52% average TPH removal after 4 weeks of study is in agreement with the study by [19] which reported 43% using an organic nutrient for TPH concentration of 60,000mg/kg while 3000 and 30,000mg/kg TPH contaminated soils showed variations in removal efficiencies with 52% and 58% average removal efficiencies respectively after 90days. The findings by [19] showed that TPH concentration above 30,000mg/kg is toxic to the microbial community which reduced the rate of biodegradation. Similarly, [20] and [21] recorded 55%, and 52% average removal efficiencies using sewage sludge after 9 and 10 weeks study period respectively which also corresponds to the results of the present BSTc study. This showed that the use of organic substrate (wastewater) results in effective TPH removal when compared to the control treatment.

4 Conclusion

The amendment of wastewaters stimulates the contaminated environment which enhanced mineralization for hydrocarbon degradation. Brewery wastewater recorded a 2% increase in TPH removal efficiency more than municipal wastewater. The removal efficiencies (48-58%) recorded with the amendment of wastewater signified reduction of TPH concentration below the extreme toxic limit. The study showed that wastewater can serve as a potential strategy for the treatment and reclamation of crude oil-contaminated soil.

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